
PROFESSIONAL SKILLS OF LIS PROFESSIONAL FOR PROVIDING QUALITATIVE LIBRARY SERVICES

Shivaji Maruti Shinde.

Shivraj College of Pharmacy, Gadhinglaj.

Corresponding Author - Shivaji Maruti Shinde.

Email- shivajirao.shinde@gmail.com

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.7179944

Abstract:

An invention of printing press as well as advent of computer and subsequent development in Information Communication Technology library and information Centre are now knowledge hub. To work the organization smoothly and discharge the duties satisfactorily as per user's Point of view their needs a dynamic skillful media person called information professionals.

Keywords: Professional Skills, LIS Professional, Knowledge, Information, Quality Library Service.

Introduction:

From the above quote by T S Eliot we can understand the value of knowledge and information. After, an invention of the printing press by Johannes Gutenberg in 1440 literature published drastically in every field of knowledge. As a result library and information centre came into existence. Later the advent of computer and rapid developments in information and communication technology, knowledge became the power. Besides, library and information centre's became more and more sophisticated with newer technology. It is in this context library and information professional plays a vital role.

Profession: According to Oxford English Dictionary, a profession is a vocation requiring knowledge of some department of learning or science. Utilizing this definition to librarianship we can say that library and information is a service oriented occupation where an individual earns money by providing services to the patron of the library.

Professional Skills: Professional skills are a combination of both Hard Skills and Soft Skills. Those who obtain these skills, Professional becomes better leaders, solve problems at work, resolve conflicts and enable the team and personal growth.

Professional Skills for LIS Professionals: Today's libraries are very closely effected by modern ICT tools, networking programmes, and skillful human resources. Since the library services are vital for teaching and research, it is essential that important areas like information resources, human resources, Application Technology, Resource Sharing, Management System, Planning of different services etc. should be given proper attention on a priority basis. To meet all these requirements high quality library professionals are needed to provide library services within a short span of time.

Professional skills are categorized into Four Broad Groups,

1. Technical Skills.

2. Leadership and Management Skills.
3. Information skills.
4. Soft Skills.

Now we will elaborate these skills one by one.

1. Technical Skills:

- i) Knowledge about different operating system like windows, Linux, Unix etc.
- ii) Database Management Software.
- iii) Application Software.
- iv) Web-Page Designing
- v) Use of search engine and search strategies
- vi) Use of Electronic database, E-books, E-Journals.
- vii) Electronic Document Delivery Service.

2. Leadership and Management Skills:

- i) General Managerial Skills.
- ii) Research and Project Management Skills.
- iii) Resource Management Skill
- iv) Personnel and financial Management Skill
- v) Effective leadership Skill
- vi) Time Management Skill
- vii) Marketing Skill

3. Information Skill:

- i) Collection information Management Skill.
- ii) Information Management Skill.
- iii) Information Retrieval Skill.
- iv) Digital Reference and Information Service Skill.
- v) Information Literacy Skill.
- vi) Information Evaluation Skill
- vii) Information Analysis Skill

4. Soft Skills:

- i) Ability to accept lean from objective criticism.
- ii) Acceptance of others.
- iii) Acting as a team player
- iv) Behaviour traits; attitude and motivation.
- v) Communication skills
- vi) Creativity / Innovation

- vii) Custom service oriented
- viii) Diagnostic insight
- ix) Emotional Management
- x) Have a winner attitude
- xi) Influencing skill
- xii) Keeping your boss informed.
- xiii) Motivate yourself and lead others.
- xiv) Problem Solving
- xv) Risk taking skill
- xvi) Stress Management
- xvii) Team development Management.
- xviii) Trust and Rapport building
- xix) Winning Commitment.

Professional Skills

Total Quality Management in

Library: Total quality Management is a concept which makes quality and responsibility of all circles within an organization. All the persons involved are expected to contribute to the overall improvement of quality. It is a preferred method to increase the satisfaction of the users. It reduces the defects of the organization and increases the productivity.

Guidelines of NAAC on Quality

Library Services: To sustain and development of quality library services National Accreditation Council gaining momentum in our country. In the institutional accreditation process library is the heart of the institution. Realizing the value and importance of a well equipped library and its role in higher education NAAC has given following guidelines:

- a) Working hours.
- b) Library advisory Committee.
- c) Collections of books, journals, non book materials as prescribed by the apex body. (UGC, AICTE, PCI etc)
- d) **Services-** Library should provide the publication and research support services , information display and notifications, Bibliographic Compilation, Inter- library loan/ Resource Sharing ,Reprographic facilities, Book Bank, User orientation, OPAC, Indexing services, Audio-Visual resources.
- e) **Internet-** Digital library Services, Ratio of library books of student enrolled, Number of login's into the e-library service, e-documents delivered per month. Network of academic libraries under universities jurisdiction. Members of library network (Inflibnet, Delnet)

Qualitative Library Services: Modern Library's and information centre are known as service institution. The main purpose is to attract the readers and use library resources. These libraries acquire print and non-print materials process it and make it available for the users rather than preservation. It allows open access to its collection and provides services to users.

Following are the services performed usually.

- Bardcoding and QR Code
- CAS and SDI.
- SMS Service
- Document Scanning
- Electronic Document Delivery
- Indexing and Abstracting
- Translation
- Micrographic and Reprographic

- Online Public Access Catalogue
- Blogs Service
- Vodacasting-Video on demand
- Instant Messages.
- E-Mail
- Reference and Referral Service

Conclusion:

Thus, we have seen the importance of professional skill. From a lay man to a specialized the professionals provide the right information to the right reader at the right time. These three 'R' are crucial for providing qualitative library services. Since independence the Government of India fosters the education system in the country. But the whole gamut to interlink education is the library professionals and the services they provide to library community. So education and library are the twin sisters.

References:

1. Gupta, O. P. (1998): Library and Information Services in University And College Libraries In India: Modernisation of Library Services Traced by planning commission In India (1st ed.), Annexure-XII, Reliance, P.215 .
2. Obt. Gupta, O. P. (1998): Library and Information Services in University And College
3. Libraries India: In india: Future Library And Information Services(1st ed.),
4. chapter –VI, Reliance. P.178.
5. Lata ,suresh (2010) Manual for knowledge custodians chapter-

- I, International Library Standards , Shruti, P.50.
6. Obt.Lata, Suresh (2010) Manual for Knowledge Custodians. Guidelines on quality indicators in library. Shruti , P 278.
 5. Gurav, Aarati (2014) Time Management Guide to Managing your time. Buzzingstock, P132-140.
 7. Vilas Jadhav, Mahesh Gaikwad. (2014) Challenges before Academic Library Professionals Working in Maharashtra. Changing Trends in Academic Libraries and Librarianship in Digital Environment. 377-381
 8. Krishna Kumar (1978) Reference service.P.1 Vikas.
 9. Obt. Krishna Kumar (1978) Reference service. P.2 Vikas.
 10. Shinde, S M.(2019) New Horizon Annual Magazine, Library the Harbinger of Education. Vinay Graphics ,P42.
 11. Rosario, P J Vasantha Kumar. (2012, july)Shodhganga; ICT Skills among library professionals in Digital era. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/90017>
 12. International Journal of Digital Library Services 4(3), P1-8.
 13. Kurade, Sandeep (2019, july) Digital duniya – granthalyatilkhajinaekavatlahat iSakalvardhapandinvishesh.
 14. Retrieved from <https://zety.com/blog/professional-skills>.